

FORSIGHT METHOD IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC PLANNING
IN COMPANIES WITH THE HELP OF CORPORATE

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Current globalization of the world economy requires significant materialistic and financial matters, labor resources and many economic and political factors in order to attain high results. Those who are well acquainted with the ongoing economic reforms and economic policy in our country believe that such a basis exists and the intended goal can be achieved.

Of particular importance is the modernization and diversification of the economy, the creation of new production facilities as a result of attracting foreign investment and capital, the improvement of management practices, i.e. enforcing principles of international business conduction.

At present, all large enterprises in the Republic are transformed into joint-stock companies and the number of economic entities under modern corporate governance methods is increasing day by day. This contributes to the rapid development of the economy, the increase in industrial potential, the development of sectors based on high technologies, in other words, the increase in the competitiveness of economic entities operating in various sectors of the economy of our country.

It is known that the introduction of modern management technologies in business entities cannot be carried out without the introduction of data collection mechanism, processing and rapid provision of relevant analytical accounting information, which will be base for strategic decision-making by managers.

As a result of the globalization of Japan and the intensification of market competition around the world, there is a growing need for strategical management of the economy. The process of implementing strategic management involves the extensive use of a number of methods, the most relevant of which today is the foresight method.

The term foresight¹⁰, translated from English, means “to look to the future” and means to be able to see the future state of a particular process or event.

The foresight method is used as a key that is determined based on a wide-ranging survey conducted by experts based on the economic and social situation of any region. This, in turn, brings enormous social and economic benefits to society and the state. In European countries, the concept of corporate foresight method is widely used in both large corporate structures and small and medium-sized businesses.

According to the study, European experts use foresight method as an active tool for studying the future. Corporate foresight is considered an important factor in planning the future of companies.

What are the important aspects of foresight? According to the official website of the European Commission, foresight has the following important aspects in the management of companies¹¹:

- considering the possibility of combining the impact of decisions made in the company with other changes;

- providing operational information to the company's management, supporting and developing policies in various areas;

social requirements and problems, etc.

Corporate foresight is one of the new forms of business management mechanisms in companies, helping them to adapt to the unpredictable changes of the competitive environment and strengthen their position in the dynamically changing global market in the long run. In addition, corporate foresight involves identifying, monitoring and analyzing the factors that cause future changes for companies, timely identifying the impact of potential external factors, and taking appropriate action.

Foresight technology is a system based on prediction methodology. Over the past 10 years, it has become a widely used tool in political, strategic planning and management around the world.

It should be noted that before using a foresight, it is necessary to clearly define its purpose. In this way, one can choose effective methods of foresight and start practical actions. This can be seen in the examples given in the UN Guide to Foresight as a Strategic Long-Term Planning Tool for Developing Countries. In particular, in 1998, Brazil conducted its first experiment on foresight. In 1996, the Government of India also started implementing this program. In both countries, the

¹⁰ Foresight (an English foresight means - to see the future) process of knowing the long-term prospects of science, technology and innovation in a systematic way

¹¹ <http://sov-europe.ru/images/pdf/2017/06-2017/>

program is called "Technology 2020", and we can see from the current stages of development of these countries that the 23-25-year development plans were developed using the foresight method.

The most widely used methods of foresight in developed countries are "Delphi", "Important technologies", "Expert panel". These methods allow the identification of key trends using an analysis aimed at studying the interaction of variable drivers - STEEPV¹².

For example, we can consider the case of Nokia, which failed to notice the changing trend in the market in a timely manner. The company, which has had a foothold in the mobile technology market in the recent past, has failed to maintain its position in the global market in the period of industry change. Nokia, owing one of the most advanced corporate foresight systems in Europe, failed to compete with Apple in the mid-2000s in the mobile phone market. Such an unconditional defeat can be explained by the fact that the company failed to determine the future of the business it manages, and made a mistake in defining clear responsibility and accountability for the corporate foresight unit.

In recent years, it can be pointed out that the Delphi prediction method has become widespread as one of the most popular methods of foresight. This method is based on a survey of specialists in a particular field (2-3 thousand people), as well as feedback from them in the second phase of the survey. This method of prediction is also widely used in research conduction. The Delphi method is actively used in Germany, Japan, the United Kingdom and some other countries. In order to achieve a positive result, highly qualified specialists will be selected for the survey, expert commissions will be formed in certain regions and a list of long-term (twenty-five to thirty years) social, economic, scientific and technological achievements will be developed¹³.

The experts involved in the study evaluate each topic, determining whether the necessary resources are available. Obstacles that may occur in the implementation of an important direction are identified.

It should be noted that today another method of predicting future changes, called "Important technologies", is widely used, mainly in France, the United States, the Czech Republic and some other countries. The essence of this method is that the formation of the necessary information for the company is based on the knowledge of highly qualified specialists. They list important technologies in research areas. Typically, not many experts are involved in making such a prediction. In addition, the prospects for forecasting are designed for a period of five to ten years.

¹² STEEPV - social, technological, economical, environmental, political, values.

¹³ Kuklina I.R. Regional Foresight as a Tool for Creating Technology Clusters in the Regions: Dokl. M., 2008. -120 p.

It needs to be noted that another way to predict future changes is through the Expert Panel. Recently, most predictive projects are being developed using the "expert panel" method. A team of 12 to 20 experts will be formed to implement this method. Experts are invited to a specific topic and given time (e.g., a month) to develop possible options for the future. This provides access to the latest information-analytical developments and materials.

A distinctive feature of the Expert Panel method is that the forecasting process itself is an open data system for many. The main advantage of the method is that it represents the interaction of different fields of activity and scientific disciplines, which are very difficult to organize in other conditions.

In the late 1970s, Motorola developed a new method of forecasting. It can also be called a "road map". It can also be used as a key area for developing long-term strategies for large companies or technology industries. The essence of this method is to plan all the key components of the business. This method can be used effectively in the development of finance, marketing, technology, engineering infrastructure, markets and services. The main advantage of creating roadmaps is that it creates a constant vision of the long-term development goals of the company and allows it to be monitored.

In today's era of globalization, large companies are doing positive implementations to strengthen their ability to adapt to changing market conditions. It is noteworthy that in our country the issues of wide use of strategic planning, systematic monitoring of its implementation, financing of planned measures are being considered in the development of complex measures in this area.

The experience of developed countries shows that the successful socio-economic development of the country depends in many respects on the use of strategic planning as an instrument of public administration. The basis of strategic planning is the forecasts, strategies and conceptions of the medium and long-term socio-economic development developed by each country, its regions and sectors¹⁴.

An important factor in the strategic planning of economic development of the country is the development of a long-term development strategy. The development strategy is an instrument for creating the future of the nation, which sets clear goals, priorities and objectives of economic policy, taking into account the economic and social security of the country and the interests of future generations. Such program provides an opportunity to combine the actions and capabilities of public administration.

We are entering a new era of strategy, moving from strategic planning to strategic management. Implementing strategic planning using a combination of foresight involves not only company executives, but also managers and

¹⁴ Kostav U.U. Directions of strategic development of Uzbekistan and the role of strategic management accounting in their implementation / Electronic journal of the National News Agency of Uzbekistan, August 2020. - 34 p.

professionals. This allows for a detailed study of problems, clear goals, and the development of alternatives using a foresight strategy.

All enterprises, organizations and companies need to develop their own long-term strategies and gradually implement strategic planning. This, in turn, provides far-sightedness in a rapidly changing market environment. Hence, the role of corporate foresight in determining this long-term perspective is enormous.

In general, corporate foresight serves to detect changes and signals that cannot be detected using standard tools, i.e., it plays an additional role in relation to existing strategy formulation tools.

Another important area in the strategic planning process is marketing. This is because in the implementation of this cycle, marketing provides the company with the necessary information and needs. Strategic planning is closely related to foresight. The reason is that if we consider foresight as an instrument of future development, strategic planning can be introduced as a complex program that includes a sequence of systematic work of this development.

In the past 2020-2021, all countries of the world faced unexpected situation. As a result, it is no secret that the GDP growth rate in most countries has fallen sharply.

Ford, a world-renowned automobile manufacturer, is partnering with GE Healthcare to produce a range of medical devices during today's pandemic. In particular, it is producing devices to help the human respiratory system, especially patients with COVID-19, face shields and other medical personal protective equipment. In this way, the company was able to maintain its flexibility in a changing market environment.

It should be noted that today the growth of investment flows is exacerbated by factors that can limit the growth of the global economy, such as the slowdown in the world economy, the problems of debt and budget deficits in Europe, uncertainty about the fate of foreign exchange rates and rising risks in financial markets. Particular attention will be paid to the following three areas of investment attraction and effective use in developed countries:

- development of import substitution strategy;
- strengthening basic industries and export potential;
- Development of science and innovation.

In this regard, the investment strategy of the Republic of South Korea is noteworthy. The country has pursued a policy of effective use of foreign investment in the process of attracting investment from developed countries, including the United States and Japan, in order to apply effective management methods and production technology in these countries.

In addition, developed countries have a rich experience in investment activities, the effective use of which in the practice of Uzbekistan will improve the practice of attracting foreign investment and further increase the efficiency of investment.

It is natural that the implementation of the positive directions of investment policy in developed countries in national practice will have a certain positive effect. In particular, the experience of Japanese investment policy is notable for its importance. In this regard, one of the important priorities of investment policy in our country is the introduction of advanced equipment and technologies on the basis of long-term projects to attract foreign investment.

In conclusion, strategic planning and foresight are the most effective tools in developing solutions to issues that are currently crucial. Along with strategic planning in our country, an important requirement for development is the creation of a normative framework for the foresight method and its new mechanisms, which are evaluated as a methodology of the future and experienced by developed countries.

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